

The Impact Of Celta Course On Enriching Efl Students' Vocabulary Learning With Reflection To The Guided Discovery Sheet Approach

Abdulghani Eissa Tour Mohammed

Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: November 15, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: January 02 , 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords CELTA, guided discovery sheet , inductive , deductive, blocking vocabulary</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4410663</p>	<p><i>The current study aims at implementing the guided discovery sheet as an approach that basically addresses meaning, pronunciation and form (MPF) of the target language. The guided discovery sheet approach provides students an opportunity to work freely with guidance descending from the teaching practice sessions we had a long the journey towards the development of a global English language-teaching profession which represented in the accomplishment of CELTA course during the summer of 2018. CELTA is a course runs by Cambridge Assessment English, a department of Cambridge University and refers to "Certificate in Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages". To undertake this study, the approach has been practiced in practice during the academic year (1442 - 1443 H), to teach a course under the title "Effective Academic writing 2" which was taught to students of level (2) at College of Science & Arts, Ar Rass, Qassim University, Saudi Arabia. Afterwards a qualitative method is adopted through which the researcher interviewed the same group of students numbering (33) via the Blackboard platform. The interview questions strike the strengths and the weaknesses associated with the implementation of the guided discovery sheet approach in learning the vocabulary of the target language. The study subjects confirmed that the approach was interesting and enabled them to learn the blocking vocabulary in a very attractive way and they recommended its application in all their academic writing classes.</i></p>

1. Introduction

As far as the researcher knows, learner – centred approaches are rarely applicable at Qassim University, for instance, most of EFL classes at College of Science and Arts, Ar Rass are still carried out via lecturing approach where teachers dominate the entire allocated time for EFL classes. Moreover, most of the classes are organized in a very traditional way with little teaching and learning facilities and are ranging from large to very, very large ones. Being a part of CELTA course, the researcher has taught 6 practical hours using a number of teaching approaches including the guided discovery sheet as a requirement of the course that consists of 200 guided learning hours. Therefore, with reflection to the researcher's teaching experiences, we can simply say that the approach is mainly a learner – centred one which provide students a great opportunity to learn the language deductively and inductively. We can also say that candidate who apply for the CELTA course experience a very different situation of teaching settings compared to the traditional classes where the researcher had experienced at Qassim University. For instance, after awarding CELTA qualification, the researcher becomes aware of how to increase the students' talking time (STT) and decrease the teacher's talking time (TTT) in normal classes as well as the large ones. Descending from the researcher's accumulative experience in teaching the blocking vocabulary of the target language either deductively or inductively, teaching approaches such the guided discovery sheet seem to be not comparable to the traditional ones where the instructors dominated the entire time allocated for the EFL class. The researcher has notified the enormous difference between the traditional teaching methodologies versus the communicative language teaching (CLT) after experiencing the CELTA course. Therefore, it comes out that teaching language (grammar & vocabulary via adopting the guided discovery approach, meaning, pronunciation and form (MPF) of the target language is clarified before learners actually engage in problems solving activities. However, the process of students' engagement in active learning through self-reliance is simply ignore by most of the traditional approaches. In fact, one of the most important advantages of implementing the communicative language learning approaches in EFL classes is to inspire students to work energetically without totally relying on the instructor.

Statement of the study problem

Implementing approaches such as the guided discovery sheet certainly enables students to apply the rules of the target language and work actively to solve problems based on a given context. Unlike the traditional classes where lecturing approach is the main EFL meal for most of the teachers while students are just passive listeners,

the guided discovery sheet approach is more learner – centred. With reflection to the researchers' teaching practices (TPs), classroom observations, and the accumulative feedback from tutors as well as teacher trainees, we can simply say that what had been used inside the classroom before the CELTA course were mainly teacher – centred approaches. Thus, the current study attempts to investigate the strengths of the guided discovery sheet approach to enable students work actively based on a given context within a shape of classes where every single student has the opportunity to participate working with at least some peers. Thus, traditional large classes won't make such dreams come true compared to today's standard EFL classes that purposefully take a shape of a horseshoe to meet the requirements of the communicative learning approach. Lack of rapport is also common in large classes similar to the ones where 50/ 80 students are regularly enrolled at College of Science and Arts, Ar Rass up to present. When dealing with large classes, for instance, it is challenging to control the class, and predominantly welcome the late comers politely.

Lack of supporting students to engage with the subject being taught and, more deeply, identifying students' names are also among the challenges that may prevent the formation of a strong rapport particularly in large classes. Therefore, it makes sense to say that traditional teaching methods such as grammar translation won't empower teachers to clarify meaning of the target language and that is why students of level 2 at Qassim University, where the researcher is currently work, find it difficult to write a short essay. However, the learners' vocabulary building skills were impressive when implementing the guided discovery sheet approach to illuminate the (MPF) of the blocking vocabulary with reflection to the academic writing course book. These remarkable results are clearly stated by Spencer, (1999, p. 186), who summarizes the approach's key features as follows: initially when dealing with the guided discovery sheet approach, a context that suits students' learning outcomes is provided, they are encouraged towards problem solving activities via using the context to understand the target language through self- directed learning. The guided discovery sheet aims at facilitating the students' mission towards learning, and finally, their understanding is measured through controlled tasks, reinforcement of problem solving, and/or the implementation of problem – oriented task based. Hence, the present study may be significant as it aims to inspire EFL professors at Qassim University in particular to adopt the most innovative teaching approaches such as the guided discovery sheet when teaching the target language as well as other language skills. Consequently, communicative language teaching approaches motivate learners to engage freely in discovering the requested rules within any given context.

3. Study questions

This study will attempt to answer the following questions:

- 1- To what extent the implementation of the guided discovery sheet approach is efficient compared to other approaches had been experienced in EFL classes?
- 2- How did the approach enable students to learn some vocabulary building techniques?
- 3- How were concept checking questions effectual simplifying meaning understanding?

4. Literature Review

Although the literature review shows various definitions of the guided discovery sheet approach, however, the following quotation from the British Council website simply clarifies it.

'Guided discovery, also known as an inductive approach, is a technique where a teacher provides examples of a language item and helps the learners to find the rules themselves'

The approach is also defined by Mayer (2003, p. 88) as a teaching approach that inspire students to learn actively when working on activities designed to encourage them to solve the problems and to discover the rules themselves via answering a chain of questions. The two definitions emphasize indirectly the important role of forming a learner –centred class that allows students to explore the rules of the target language themselves and reduce the role of the teachers. In so doing, teachers also establish a friendly atmosphere and strength connection with learners the thing which certainly motives their learning. This type of connection is also known as rapport. As it is declared by Scrivener there are different kinds of teachers and of course different kinds of teaching, too. Accordingly, both teachers and learners on one hand, and learners themselves on the other hand, relate to each other in different ways. To understand these differences Scrivener, (2005), puts forth the following questions: - What is behind the distinctive atmosphere of each teacher's class?

- How a defensive and anxious classroom is different compared to a class where everyone feels able to be honest and takes risks? These questions and many more remind us about the importance of creating a friendly atmosphere where students can effectively be engaged and have a strong rapport. *"Teachers and trainers often comment on the importance of 'rapport' between teachers and students"*(Scrivener, 2005, pp.22-23).

However, the definition of the term rapport is still complicated despite the fact that it is clearly important. Rapport is sometimes defined in terms of a situation where teachers are generally being friendly to their students. According to Scrivener who also believes that the above definition is a reasonable starting point, but concerning many more aspects associated with the quality of how teachers and learners relate, still we need to find a wider definition for the term rapport.

Leaning on past experience, the researcher has been enrolled in the authorized centre of the Institute of Language Studies (International House) Izmir, Turkey in 2018 and becomes conscious of clarifying the course requirements in this section as follows: first it is a two components assess course based on planning and teaching, not neglecting classroom – related written assignments.

It addresses five areas as follows:

1. Learners and teachers, and the teaching and learning context.
2. Language analysis and awareness.
3. Language skills: reading, listening, speaking and writing.
4. Planning and resourcing for different teaching contexts.
5. Developing teaching skills and professionalism.

CELTA has principles of teaching which are applicable for both language and its receptive as well as productive skills. The course provides an ideal opportunity for its candidates to work with numerous language teaching approaches. Among these approaches are the test teach test (TTT), Present practice produce (PPP), and language from the text which are useful and effective when it comes to teaching grammar, vocabulary or language function. In total these approaches are mainly address the importance of illuminating the (MPF).

Moreover, they are also followed by errors correction at the final stage, and under the instructor's instructions, students have to conduct either controlled or free practice in different stages. Both the receptive skills and the productive ones share the gist activity or tasks in different stages. The interesting thing is that practical teaching is done either deductively or inductively. Richards et al, 1985, define both the deductive and the inductive learning approaches clearly by stating that when teaching students, the rules of the target language before providing them specific information and ask them to apply the given rules in different tasks, we are refereeing to the deductive approach. However, when such rules are not taught directly and students are asked to induce them descending from their experience in using the target language, it is a time for inductive approach.

The above definition takes the researcher back to the input sessions where we were taught how to reduce the (TTT) and increase the (STT) during the CELTA course. Thus, an inductive approach such as the guided discovery sheet is a good example of an approach which its implementation in EFL classes enables teachers to organize a learner – centred class rather than a teacher – centred one particularly when teaching grammar and vocabulary. Throughout the CELTA course, the target language is clarified via the illuminating meaning in context to empower students getting the rules themselves and confirm their understanding through using a type of questions known as concept checking questions. Afterwards the instructor has to clarify how to form the language items simply to avoid meaningless questions such as “do you understand? or is it clear? Which are somehow associated with traditional teaching approaches where the teacher provides a rule via giving an example and ask students to practice using them based on the given representations. A task based on a guided discovery sheet approach can turn an EFL class into a learner – centred one, simply because it gives them the opportunity to work self-sufficiently with the target language as they have to discover the rules and reinforce collaborative learning strategy through a clear inductive process. The approach also contributes to the communicative language teaching since it reduces the role of the teacher to the extent that he/she can only intervene when it is necessary. Furthermore, Al-Kharrat, (2000), investigates the importance of teaching the language rules either deductively and inductively to highlight the influence of the two approaches on how students can strongly involve in the process of learning the target language through maximizing their opportunities to practice thinking. The variety of communication strategies associated with the two approaches deductive and inductive on the other hand, replace the learners' L2 knowledge gap as clearly stated by (Harmer, 1989). As stated above students are highly considered when teaching language (grammar, vocabulary or functions), following various CELTA course methodology. Virtually, when applying the (ppp) approach, the instructor kicks off the lesson with a lead in as a trigger to catch students' attention through creating a setting context and personalise a topic under instruction. To undertake the current study, the researcher used the guided discovery sheet approach to simplify the blocking vocabulary or language function of the target language as it is found that through implementation of such approaches, reinforcement of a collaborative learning environment among students is developed (Peck, 1988). A presentation of (MPF) is then followed, and it is a stage where the teacher enlightens the students' understanding of the target language via a reading passage or different written examples displayed to the students. Initially, meaning is dealt with simply because students may find it difficult to learn the pronunciation or the form of some language if they don't actually know the meaning. To simplify meaning and confirming that students are aware of it, the instructor conducts some concept checking questions (CCQS), usually a short yes/ no questions and simple ones aiming at checking students' understanding of what is being taught. For example, after teaching present perfect tense in meaningful sentence, “**Ali has been to Riyadh**”, the instructor may ask students the following yes/ no questions to check their understanding of the tense usage:

- A. Is Ali still in Riyadh now? No
- B. Was he in Riyadh? Yes

These types of questions are always work and regarded as tools for developing the language awareness of students. Moreover, they are more effective and efficient methods of checking how learners understood something rather than asking them "Do you understand?" when they may think they do but actually they do not, they may also feel shy or reluctant to say loudly that they have not understood particularly in front of their classmates simply because they may laugh at him/her (Graham Workman, 2005). Almost, the researcher illustrates the (MPF) in a section titled "summary and findings". For instance, the pronunciation of some words is drilled in meaningful sentences individually as well as in chorus. Additionally, researcher elicits the form of some suggested words reminding students how to reflect on parts of speech. Given, some students have successfully stated that "independently" in the given context is an adjective.

Furthermore, CELTA course also addresses the (ICQS), instruction checking questions; these are kinds of questions raised to make sure that students are aware of the teacher instructions before actually starting the task. They aim at clarifying meaning and guide students for further understanding of the target language.

For instance, while reading for gist, the teacher has to guide students for further understanding of his instructions and to make sure every student knows exactly what to do. Possibly, the teacher can ask them the following questions.

A. Are you going to read silently and individually? Yes

B. Are you going to read every single word? No

The importance of both (CCQS) and (ICQS) is simply ignored when Comparing between a communicative language teaching approaches and the traditional ones where everything is conducted and dominated by the instructors. Celce-Murcia et al (1997), believe that the former provides a better environment. The vast literature review shows that both the deductive and inductive approaches are intuitively very attractive, therefore, their great impact as communicative methods is unquestionably instrumental simply because they create an ideal atmosphere for learners to communicate freely.

Moreover, clarifying the (MPF) meaning, pronunciation and form is followed by more practice to make sure that students are now able to work with the target language efficiently, so the instructor needs to give them the opportunity to use it accurately and repeatedly via practicing. In this stage, a controlled practice is conducted where students work in pairs or in groups to complete a given task. Meanwhile, the instructor observes closely and encourages them to produce the target language and also to take notes for the delayed feedback. For example, let us assume that he/she has shown the students the form and the use of the third person singular (s), they now do a fill in task using its structure.

e.g.

He usually (go)to school. I regularly (play) Tennis. To have students state their ideas clearly addressing the fluency in the target language, a freer practice in which students move towards completing communication activities freely is required. Again, the role of the teacher in this stage is to encourage and reshape the groups or the partners to create more communicative opportunities between the students. For instance, while communicating freely, the teacher has to direct them towards the form and the use of the third person singular (s).

A final feedback is given for addressing students' errors that required some forms of correction. These kinds of errors could be the ones observed or written by the teacher during the two different stages. His/her ultimate goal then is to overcome the suggested errors and to give an overall feedback.

As a teaching approach, (TTT) aims at determining what students do and do not already know about the target language. It seems very rare to teach students a language component where no one in class has ever come across anything at all. Before the teacher chooses to actively deal with the target language in the classroom, at least limited learners if not the majority of them have had an exposure to most language that they are going to study at their level. Therefore, it seems very logical not to waste students' time teaching them something they already know, instead the focus is going to be on the parts they don't know or can't do. As usual, such a lesson starts with a brief lead - in that helps student personalise the topic under instruction. So, a teacher is going to determine their strengths and weaknesses via controlling practice test which is organised and distributed to the students to check whether they are able to use the target language correctly or not.

Example:

Use the verb in brackets () correctly in the past simple tense form.

Yesterday, I (go)to the fruits market where I (buy).....some bananas and oranges. It (be) really easy to get there. When I came back we (be)a nice lunch.

During this stage students work individually to complete the task, meanwhile, the teacher observes the situation carefully to decide on their weaknesses as well as their strengths in dealing with the simple past tense. Forming the past tense of regular verbs might not be problematic for the majority of the students, but they may find it difficult when it comes to the past tense of some irregular verbs. That is why teachers need to monitor learners carefully to determine their weak points. Students then compare their answers with partners; however, monitoring is seen as a vital role of the teacher during this stage to know what is the most needed in the next stage.

The teaching stage is aiming at clarifying the (MPF) of the target language. Nevertheless, it is extremely important to focus on are the difficulties encounter by the students during the test stage. For example, if learners showed difficulties in forming the past tense of the irregular verbs, the teacher has to pay attention to such difficulties while teaching to overcome them. Other possibility is that students will have some difficulties with the pronunciation of the verbs ending – ed which seems to be a common problem among learners. Whatever the problem is, it is the role of the teacher to decide when to intervene and clarify the target language.

Regarding the second test, the researcher can say that it aims at enabling students to use the language successfully. It is usually similar to the first one, with a controlled practice where students are expected to do effectively since they have covered the most challenging parts during the teaching stages. So far, the teacher has seen some improvement in terms of the understanding as well as the accurate usage of the target language. Thus, a freer practice tasks are conducted to give students the real practicing opportunities for more fluency of language production through providing such tasks.

The third approach for teaching grammar, vocabulary or language functions is to adopt a method known as teaching “language from a text” (T B Task-Based). As the name suggests, in this method we need to allow students to see the language in context and then act similarly to produce their own works. Our context in this situation will be a written or a spoken text where students can either read or listen to something which naturally contains good examples of the target language.

Example:

Sami is a Saudi EFL students. He studies English at Riyadh internal language centre. He regularly goes to the institutes by car. He likes the way English is taught and often encourages me to join them. I am attempting to be enrolled during the upcoming summer vacations.

5. Material and methods

To undertake this study, the guided discovery sheet approach has been applied in practice during the academic year (1442 -1443 H), to teach a course under the title “Effective Academic writing 2” which is taught to students of level (2) at College of Science & Arts, Ar Rass, Qassim University, Saudi Arabia. Afterwards a qualitative method is adopted through which the researcher interviewed the same group of students numbering (33) via the Blackboard platform. The interview questions aim at determining the strengths and the weaknesses associated with the implementation of the guided discovery sheet approach in learning the vocabulary of the target language. Moreover, the researcher has highlighted the strengths of CLTA course teaching methodologies via conducting a workshop hosted by ArRass Educational directorate during the academic year (1441-1442 H). The workshop was attended by (40) EFL teachers. Through an intensive discussion and feedback, the majority of the participants advocated the strengthening role of the Saudi students in self-learning to minimize the constant teacher intervention during classes and finally greed that CELTA teaching approaches will be effective when implemented in EFL different settings.

The following questions were put forward for the data collection procedures.

- 1- To what extent the implementation of the guided discovery sheet approach is efficient compared to other approaches had been experienced in EFL classes?
- 2- How did the approach enable students to learn some vocabulary building techniques?
- 3- How were concept checking questions effectual simplifying meaning understanding?

Table 1: A guided discovery worksheet (1)

<p><u>My story</u></p> <p>Last year I and my brother decided to travel abroad. Actually, I am not good at organizing my things, therefore, I decided to consult <u>a guided tour</u>. My brother, on the other hand, likes to go a lone so he traveled <u>independently</u>. I also work for an oil company, so I like to travel <u>first class</u>. But my brother is a student and that is why he decided to travel <u>economy class</u>. Additionally, I like everything to be organized, accordingly, I paid a fixed price for my <u>package holiday</u>. Fortunately, my <u>journey</u> lasted for two months, while my brother's <u>trip</u> was very short, and lasted for only two weeks.</p>

The above table illustrates a context through which the researcher aims to teach some blocking vocabulary as well as phrases adopting the guided discovery sheet approach. Based on practical teaching, the researcher applies the approach on a prescribed textbook titled “*Effective Academic Writing-2*” to a group of English major students at Qassim University during the academic year (1442-1443H). The course aims to help students improve their overall academic writing skills through writing comparison-contrast, cause-and-effect, argumentative, classification, and reaction five-paragraph essays. According to the course specification, students have to prepare in class portfolio out of (5) written essays as a course requirement. However, some students find it challenging particularly when it comes to vocabulary building and sentence structure. These challenges have been determined through the researcher’s assessments of the written essays as well as the constant observations throughout some in classroom activities. Therefore, the need to overcome such difficulties inspired the researcher to implement the guided discovery sheet approach aiming at improving the students’ overall writing skills.

Meaning: *What does the target language mean... in this context?*

1. **A guided tour:** if someone takes you on a guided tour, they show you around a place of interest and tell you all about it.
2. **To travel independently:** it is travel in which you organize things yourself, rather than using a company who will arrange flights, hotels etc.
3. **To travel first class:** is when someone books the best and most expensive seats on a plane or train, or the best and most expensive accommodation (place to sleep) on a ship.
4. **To travel economy class:** is when you book the cheapest seats on a plane.
5. **To go on a trip:** is often said when *going out* somewhere for a short journey abroad.
6. **To go on a journey:** is usually a long trip of some kind.
7. **A package holiday:** a holiday organized by a travel company for which you pay a fixed price that includes the cost of the hotel and travel, and sometimes food.

Checking understanding: *How will you check meaning? CCQ, clines, Timelines etc.?*

A guided tour

1. Does someone tells you about ancient places? yes
2. Does she takes you around historical buildings in the city? yes
3. Do you organize everything for yourself? no

To travel independently

1. Do you organize the trip yourself? yes
2. Do you consult a tour company to arrange it? no
3. Do you personally do the booking? Yes

To travel first class

1. Do you book the cheapest seat? no
2. Do you book the most expensive one? yes
3. Do you get above standard service? yes

To travel economy class

1. Do you book the cheapest seats in the plane? yes
2. Do you get VIP service? no
3. Do you sit on the front seats in the plane ? No

To go on a trip

1. Do you travel for a short period of time? yes
2. Do you need to book a ticket ? yes
3. Do you go out and stay for a month? No

To go on a journey

1. Do you travel for a short period of time? no
2. Do you need to book a ticket? yes
3. Do you go out and stay for one day? No

A package holiday

Table:2 (MPF) clarifications -1

Fill in gaps using the following words:

Journey – independently – guided trip -- economy class - trip – first class – a packaged - holiday

1. My brother likes to go alone, accordingly, he travels
2. I like everything to be organize, so I travel on a
3. To travelyou need to pay more money, compared to someone who travels
.....
4. When going out for a short period of time, then you go on a.....
5. If an event is organized by a travel company for which you paid a fixed price, so that is
.....
5. ais usually a long tour.

Table 3 : controlled practice task, hand out (1)

Rewrite the following sentences correctly:

1. She likes to go alone, therefore, he travels dependently. _

2. My family is enjoying summer vacation, so they decided to go in a trip.

3. We like everything to be organize, thus, we travel on a trip guided.

4. To travel economy class, you need to book a very expensive seat.

5. Our trip lasted for three years.

Table 4 : controlled practice task, hand out (2)

6. Summary and findings

Through adopting (PPP) lesson shape, the researcher kicks off the lesson with a lead-in as a trigger to catch students' attention and create a setting context that allows them to personalise the given topic displayed in table no (1). The guided discovery sheet approach has been practically implemented to clarify the blocking vocabulary of the target language, and also to reinforce a collaborative learning environment among students. A presentation of meaning, pronunciation and form is then followed, during which the researcher facilitates the understanding of the target language via reading the teacher made story. First, meaning is dealt with, simply because the earlier assessments of the written essays have revealed that students find it difficult to construct meaningful sentences and they may additionally face some difficulties to learn the pronunciation or the form of blocking vocabulary unless meaning is simplified. Afterwards the researcher conducts some concept checking questions (CCQS), actually a short yes/ no questions and simple ones to check students' understanding of what is being taught as stated in table no. (2).

Additionally, the researcher emphasizes the vital role of the (ICQS) instruction checking questions; which are kinds of questions raised to make sure that students are aware of the teacher instructions before actually starting the task. These types of questions also simplify meaning and guide students for further understanding of the target language.

Furthermore, this stage is followed by effective applications to make sure that students are now able to work with the target language, so, students were given a perfect opportunity to practice using the blocking vocabulary. For instance, in so doing, the researcher drilled the pronunciation of some suggested words in meaningful

sentences individually as well as in chorus. He also elicits the form of the same words reminding students how to reflect on parts of speech. Confidently, students have stated that "independently", for example, is an adjective based on the given context while "a package holiday" is a noun.

- | |
|---|
| <p>1- To travel independently { tu: 'trævl ,ɪndɪ'pendəntli}- (Adj)
 2- A package holiday { ə 'pækɪdʒ 'hɒlədeɪ}- (N)</p> |
|---|

Table:5 (MPF) clarifications -2

This stage is illustrated by tables (3-4) where two controlled practices tasks were basically conducted to enable students to work in pairs or in groups to accomplish the given tasks. However, due to the fact that we have been experiencing distance learning since the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic, the researcher displays the two tasks through the "Blackboard" platforms. During this stage the researcher encourages students to produce the target language and also to take notes for the delayed feedback. Aiming at empowering students to state their ideas clearly and address the fluency in the target language, a freer practice activity was provided where students were moved towards completing communication activities freely, to debate their experiences with travelling. The researcher encourages them and reshapes the groups as well as the partners to generate more communicative environment. For instance, while students debating their travel experiences, the researcher has directed them towards the form and the usage of some blocking vocabulary taught ahead. A final feedback was conducted to address students' errors that required some forms of correction. These kinds of errors were the ones observed and written by the researcher during the two different stages. Accordingly, his ultimate goal was to overcome the suggested errors and give an overall feedback.

Concerning the study subjects' responses towards the first study question, the majority believe that implementation of the guided discovery sheet approach was interesting simply because it enabled them to check their answers before receiving the feedback during several stages throughout the lesson. As stated, a head the researcher fully relied on group works as classes were covered virtually due to the ongoing pandemic. Therefore, a group checkup via the "Blackboard" platform was conducted while students' feedback and questions were taken through the chat room.

Some participants, on the other hand, think that the application of the approach assisted them to learn the meaning of the blocking vocabulary easily as they were provided in meaningful sentences. In other words, providing blocking vocabulary in a real context empowered student to learn them effortlessly. Some also confirmed that learning through the application of the guided discovery sheet approach was very effective as it encourages student to work in different settings; individually, in pairs as well as in groups during several stages, and that is why it reinforces the establishment of the learner - centred class. The study subjects also affirmed that only through the implementation of the approach they learned to differentiate between (a trip) and (a journey) simply because the two words were provided in a context. Finally, many participants have requested that such teaching approach must dominate the scene as it was very attractive and can provide any single student the opportunity to participate effectively while classes.

7. Recommendations

1. Curriculum designers in Saudi Arabia may consider the guided discovery sheet approach within their future trajectory in developing the EFL curriculum.
2. It is the time to replace the teacher – centred approaches with the learner – centred ones in EFL classes at Qassim University.
3. We extremely recommend the organization of CELTA course by Qassim University to develop its staff members' career.

8. Conclusion

To conclude this section, we can say that the implementation of the guided discovery sheet approach enables students to work independently using the target language. Practically, the study summary and the findings illustrate that study subjects were able to explore the blocking vocabulary during the controlled practice stages drawing upon their own experience and existing knowledge. Additionally, they were also managed to state their ideas clearly when provided an opportunity to share some travel related experiences during the freer practice stage. Thus, implementation of such a communicative language teaching approach is more effective and definitely generates a learner centrist setting. On the basis of the researcher's experiences and a career spanning more than two decades, we can also say that CELTA course addresses the communicative language Teaching (CLT) in such a way that motivates students to learn actively compared to the traditional language teaching and learning.

Abbreviations

CELTA: Certificate in Teaching English to Speakers of Other Languages

TP: Teaching Practice
MPF: Meaning, Pronunciation and Form
TTT: Test, Teach and Test
PPP: Presentation, Practice and Produce
CCQS: Concept Checking Questions
ICQS: Instruction Checking Questions
TTT: Teacher Talking Time
STT: Student Talking Time
TB: Task-Based

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Author Information

Dr. Abdulghani Eissa Tour Mohammed
 Department of English & Translation, College of
 Science & Arts, Ar Rass, Qassim University, Saudi
 Arabia
